

SPECIAL EDUCATION IN BASIC EDUCATION SCHOOLS: TEACHING PRACTICE AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Ana Paula Silva dos Santos Ramalho

Pedagogue at the State Department of Education of Espírito Santo – SEDU. Postgraduate student (Master's degree) at the Vale do Cricaré University Center – São Mateus (ES). Email:

anapaularamalhosdj@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This work aims to understand the acquisition of rights by people with special educational needs and how they should and can be meaningfully integrated into the teaching-learning process. It also explores how schools can play an important role in advancing the fight against exclusion by welcoming them, providing effective conditions for learning, and developing their potential. The research provides a brief history of people with special needs over the years, how the process of change has unfolded, and how laws have effectively contributed to progress in integrating these students into schools. A significant conclusion was reached, considering that change must begin with the implementation of new educational policies that demystify the concept of difference as invalid and promote the supremacy of difference as natural in every heterogeneous society, which, by its very nature, tends to mask reality. Special education should be approached from a pragmatic perspective, in which the development of public policies geared toward the target audience in question proves effective. There's no point in creating actions that appear positive in theory but prove useless to the individuals who need them, or even if teachers are unable to implement the procedures in their teaching practice.

Keywords: Educational inclusion. People with special needs. Learning. Integration.

INTRODUCTION

This work aims to understand the acquisition of rights by people with special educational needs, and how these people should and can be meaningfully integrated into the teaching-learning process. It also explores how the school can play an important role in combating exclusion, providing a welcoming environment, and offering effective conditions for learning and developing their potential.

Currently, schools are grappling with a reality that may not be what society desires. The inclusion of children with special needs in regular school classes seems to persist despite strong

arguments based on the simple fact that differences should not serve to segregate or exclude human beings from broader social interaction.

Human beings should be respected in their uniqueness, with their capacities, abilities, and potential. In life, these differences must be considered, as each individual has a different way of perceiving, understanding, and experiencing the world. The practice of social inclusion is based on principles different from the conventional ones: acceptance of individual differences, valuing each person, coexistence within human diversity, and learning through cooperation.

Inclusion should involve placing these children in the regular education system from the beginning of their school life, with a commitment to providing them with conditions for academic and social development; because, just like all other children who do not face problems related to disabilities, they exist, think, feel, and create. They cannot be deprived of real experiences that provide conditions for development that value bodily independence and emotional maturity. In this way, doubts and fears multiply among education professionals who did not receive the necessary training to understand the enormous confusion, even in the conceptualization and differentiation of terms such as special educational needs and special needs and learning difficulties.

Education for all must be carried out in an environment that fosters cognitive, linguistic, emotional, and social development. Therefore, access to information should be provided through processes that enable direct and unrestricted communication. Discriminating against a cultural minority because of their differences is a serious offense. Schools need to learn to respect people with disabilities, because only in this way can they offer a fair and equitable education.

Aware that questions and possible answers are endless, a socio-historical understanding of disability worldwide suggests understanding how some concepts have evolved to the current stage, thus serving as a reference for analyzing the inclusive process from the different perspectives currently expressed by various researchers and authors.

People with Special Needs: A Brief History

History tells us that primitive peoples subjected people with special needs (PNE), that is, individuals who manifested some impairment in some of the following areas: visual, auditory, mental or physical; to selective treatment, since, being considered a major obstacle to

the survival of the group, the PNE were murdered by some peoples. Other peoples protected and sustained those who had been mutilated in combat, in order to please the gods.

The Hebrews believed that people with disabilities represented divine punishment; therefore, they were prevented from holding religious positions. The Romans went further and, according to the *Law of the Twelve Tables*, granted patriarchs the right to kill newborn children with disabilities, just as in Sparta they threw them off cliffs. Traditionally, disability has been seen as an individual problem, and therefore, the individual would have to adapt to society or be changed by professionals through rehabilitation or cure (Fletcher, apud Sasaki, 1997).

Conversely, Hindus believed that visually impaired individuals possessed great inner sensitivity due to their lack of sight, and therefore encouraged them to pursue religious roles. Athenians, influenced by Aristotle (384-322 BC), held a much more humane view, recognizing that visually impaired individuals and the sick engaged in productive activities according to their differences. When this was not possible due to their condition, society protected and supported them. Aristotle's ideas likely influenced the Romans, as both peoples debated the appropriate course of action for visually impaired individuals: whether it should be primarily assistance or a reintegration into suitable productive activities.

Throughout history, the National Education Plan (PNE) has been subjected to various concepts and preconceptions. It has been labeled an obstacle to the perpetuation of the human species, dependent on the assistance of others, a divine punishment, or in other words, excluded; however, in modern times, the PNE is finally conceived *as a bearer of rights*.

Although traditionally these rights were reserved for the inclusion of people with disabilities as a health issue, that is, special needs were characterized as an illness. Consequently, care was restricted to specialized entities. According to Amaral (1998, p. 15), "it is necessary to recognize that normality and abnormality exist. In this way, it is necessary to think of abnormality not only as a pathology, but as an expression of human diversity."

In this sense, society has created and perpetuates various stigmas regarding the issue of people with disabilities; some are still accepted today by many individuals without question. It is necessary to create mechanisms to eliminate all these prejudices. Legal instruments are also necessary to increase the chances of inclusion for these individuals. In Brazil, Article 1, item III, of the 1988 Federal Constitution expresses the dignity of the human person as a fundamental principle of the Republic. Therefore, the issue of people with disabilities concerns the meaning and scope of this constitutional provision.

Thus, currently, people with disabilities have acquired, among many other rights, the right to professional training and rehabilitation to become qualified to obtain, retain, and

advance professionally. This is observed in Convention No. 159 of the International Labour Organization (ILO), of 1983, ratified by Brazil through Legislative Decree No. 51 of August 28, 1989, which defines a person with a disability in Article 11 as follows: "For the purposes of this Convention, 'disabled person' means any individual whose prospects of obtaining, retaining, and advancing in suitable employment are substantially reduced by reason of a duly recognized physical or mental impairment."

Disability and its concepts

When researching the history of humanity, one can see that since ancient times, individuals with disabilities have been harshly excluded. Young children and newborns who showed any sign of abnormality were despised and abandoned to their fate, becoming victims of a cruel society incapable of understanding their condition.

In the 9th and 10th centuries, exclusion was already a reality, and people considered deaf people incapable of living in society alongside those considered "normal." In Rome, fathers decided the fate of their children through their gaze. Children born with special needs were displayed in public squares and later thrown into the Tiber River or left in the fields. Regarding deaf people, for the Greco-Romans, they were not considered human beings, since they believed that thought could not occur without language.

According to this belief, based on Aristotelian ideas, thought only developed through speech, since language was what gave an individual the condition of being human; therefore, deaf people would not be able to become human, because communication with others is essential to acquiring knowledge.

Therefore, children with special needs were abandoned in public squares. Roman law excluded these children from all civil rights, classifying them as insane or mentally retarded. During the Middle Ages, sacrifices were abolished; however, discrimination persisted. People with disabilities in general were still considered non-human, even by the Catholic Church; it did not consider them immortal because they could not perform the sacraments.

EDUCATIONAL POLICY FOR SPECIAL EDUCATION

This work is based on the 1988 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Brazil, especially article 208, item III, the Statute of Children and Adolescents, Law No. 8.069 of 1990, and primarily on the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (LDBEN), Law 9.394, of

December 20, 1996. From the latter, the following determinations, applicable to the formulation of the research, are extracted:

Article 58 of the LDBEN (Brazilian Law of Education Guidelines and Bases), which characterizes special education as a modality of school education intended for students with special needs, provides, in its paragraph 1, for the existence of specialized support in regular education. For deaf people, it is necessary to fulfill the requirement of specialized support or programs in education.

Article 58: For the purposes of this Law, special education is understood to be a modality of school education, offered preferably within the regular education system, for students with special needs (Brazil, 1996). And Article 59 indicates the measures or support, of a school or assistance nature, that the education systems must ensure for students considered special. What matters in this case is the guarantee of a specialized teacher, when necessary, as determined in item III of the aforementioned article, as *follows*:

Article 59. The education systems shall ensure for students with special needs: [...] III - teachers with adequate specialization at the secondary or higher education level, for specialized care, as well as regular education teachers trained for the integration of these students in regular classes (Brazil, 1996).

From the perspective of educational policy, the present guidelines find their foundation in the Ten-Year Education Plan for All (1993-2000) and, as a pedagogical action, are supported by the National Education Plan, Law 10.172 of January 9, 2001, the National Guidelines for Special Education in Basic Education, published on September 11, 2001, the National Curriculum Parameters of 1996-1997, the National Curriculum Guidelines for Secondary Education, 1993, and the Salamanca Declaration, as recommended in Article 21.

Educational policies should take into account individual differences and diverse situations. For example, the importance of sign language as a means of communication for the deaf should be considered, and access to instruction in the sign language of their country should be ensured for all deaf people (Brazil, 1994, n.p.).

It is true that legal registration, by itself, does not guarantee rights, especially in a reality where special education has limited political expression within the context of general education. However, it is essential to be aware of the dictates of the laws in order to fight for the realization of these rights. It can be observed that in ancient times, disabled people were considered devoid of any kind of intellectual and moral capacity to even guarantee the right to their own lives and to attain an education. However, even then, Celso envisioned a possibility of education for people with disabilities.

Current national education policy favors inclusive education, that is, education organized to meet the needs of all individuals with special needs (a concept being promoted by the Ministry of Education in the media). This policy is underpinned by the Salamanca Declaration.

TEACHING PRACTICE AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The purpose of Inclusive Education is to ensure that people with disabilities, whatever they may be, have the right to develop and exercise their citizenship. In this regard, Sasaki (1997, p. 43) states that...

The prerequisite for achieving this goal is societal change. Within schools, it is quite common for professionals to feel distressed because they don't know how to deal with a student's disability, so the school starts requesting methods, techniques, and reports as a way to confirm the child's supposed disabilities.

This reveals the fragility of the institution, which seeks a reason for the student's maladjustment. The report, in this specific case, aims to justify a failure that may lie within the school itself. Regarding the report, it is important to observe what Lajonquire (2000) postulates, stating that it is always insufficient information that says nothing about the singularity of the event and also tells the teacher nothing about what to do in the classroom.

Although the author is referring to teachers' requests for pedagogical evaluations in cases of indiscipline or learning difficulties, we believe that the request for reports in inclusion cases is of the same order; it may temporarily alleviate anxiety—the author speaks of moral tranquility—but it is of no use regarding the actions of the teacher or the pedagogical coordinator. Therefore,

The claim, mainly by some pedagogical advisors, to "know," thanks to receiving a report, about the subjective singularity of a student's actions, is doomed to failure since only the child could, in the event of the case, "usefully" make use of "their" knowledge to produce, and, on the other hand, it ends up contributing to the psychologization of daily school life (Lajonquire, 2000, p. 60).

Kupffer (2001) states that educators, taking into account that their students are desiring subjects, made of original marks and inscriptions, can renounce their concern not only with method, technique, and programmatic content, but also abandon adaptation techniques, since they can accept that learning is not predetermined. However, "knowing everything does not provide the educator with a working technique, but it is certainly a guiding principle that, being

on the teacher's horizon, will modify their relationship with their student" (Kupffer, 2001, p. 26).

According to Kupffer (2004), when a teacher is giving a lesson thinking about the students who are listening and what they might be thinking of him/her, whether they are enjoying the way the lesson is being taught, it shows that we are facing a demand for love from the teacher, a demand to be recognized; undoubtedly, this involves the establishment of a loving relationship that is consequently alienating, narcissistic, and imaginary. In this way, the aforementioned author points out, there is no learning since the student has the same demand, leaving both alienated in a specular and narcissistic relationship.

Lajonquire (2000) refers to two other consequences of linkage:

- a) The adult's **resignation** from the position of educator. (...) instead of invoking the impossible of a dream – as Rubem Alves would say – or of a desire, he resigns himself to handling the education of the potential psychologist;
- b) The psychopedagogical **illusion** of natural adequacy. This illusion causes theories of child development to occupy the central place when it comes to teaching children (p. 33).

Natural adequacy proposes to complement, with its action, what is considered to be in the child in a virginal state, provided the right dose is applied. Thus, school success or failure lies in the relationship between appropriate intervention and the child's psychomaturational state. School success or failure depends on this. The author makes the illusion of claiming that modern pedagogy requires that every intervention with the child be justified in order to avoid producing frustrating effects and traumatizing the child. For him, "(...) psychopedagogical knowledge implies a natural certainty of human action. (...) thus, everything that is done must be fully justified, that is, it must be deduced as a possibility from a reality beyond educational act itself" (Lajonquire, 2000, p. 35).

The certainty of how to act in front of a child comes from psychological knowledge; however, this knowledge, found in textbooks, does not bear the mark of arbitrariness. Therefore, the teacher who acts in this way does not do so in the name of desire but rather in the name of knowledge acquired from textbooks; this results in a lack of involvement, causing the educational act to fail.

In an inclusive approach, adaptation to school content is carried out by the student themselves and demonstrates their intellectual emancipation. This emancipation is a consequence of the self-regulation process of learning, in which the student assimilates new knowledge according to their ability to incorporate it with what they already know.

Understanding this emancipatory principle of intellectual adaptation is of paramount importance for the teacher. Learning is a creative, individual, heterogeneous human action regulated by the learner, regardless of whether their intellectual condition is more or less privileged.

It is the different ideas, opinions, and levels of understanding that enrich the school process and clarify the understanding of both students and teachers. This diversity stems from the unique ways we cognitively adapt to a given subject and the possibility of expressing ourselves openly about it.

DIVERSITY: DIFFERENCE IN PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES

Reflecting on what difference is and the reasons that fuel exclusionary pedagogical stances that still permeate educational practices today, leads us to the studies of Eizirik and Comerlato (1995, p. 105) according to whom “difference is change, and it is also a profound epistemological shock, it causes pain, suffering, because it shakes the structures. In every way, difference is what momentarily puts our identity in check” (p. 105).

Educational institutions have been concerned with planning actions that can homogenize students, molding them to conform to the socially constituted order, seeking to forge their habits, interests, and motivations. From this perspective, difference, for the teacher, instead of being seen in its positive aspects, often becomes a barrier in the encounter with their students—those with whom they do not have just a casual encounter that soon ends and they can leave, but who remain in a classroom for several hours a day and many days a year. Perhaps this is why difference has provoked so many conflicts in schools.

In this regard, Foucault (1991), in his book, * *History of Madness* *, problematizes the logic that fuels the search for standardization, showing how the human being is constituted, indirectly, through the exclusion of so many others, namely: criminals, prostitutes, the elderly, the insane, the disabled. It is important to remember that this exclusion serves to confirm the distinctive *status quo* of one and the normality of another, based on the premise that what is out of step, what is different, is always the other. “Thus, the need to standardize everything seems to serve much more the satisfaction of our search for identity than our homogeneity, as a path to normal people” (Foucault, 1991, p. 78); that is, it is precisely to the extent that we characterize the other person as deviant that we ensure our supposed normality.

There are some differences that do not cause strangeness in human relations in daily school life; these are the differences that fall within a permitted social limit. It is possible to

tolerate a slightly slower pace than normal for learning to copy from the board and participate in proposed activities; however, much more difficult to accept is the difference – disability, often configured as an inability to learn and participate in common learning spaces. Thus, specifically regarding people with disabilities, it can be inferred that "[...] disability is not simply a quality present in the organism or behavior of the person considered disabled, but is defined by the nature of the relationship between this person and the one who considers them disabled" (Omoté, 1990, p. 12).

Some people with disabilities may exhibit physical features that exceed the parameters of normality of our time and culture. Often, they are subject to an impoverished perception, characterized by a disbelief in their intellectual abilities, which broadly reveals the supposed relationship between physical appearance and intellectual capacity. Within this problematic context, the teacher's perception of their students—what they think and expect from them—is not, according to Coll and Miras, merely a filter that leads them to interpret what they do in one way or another, to value their learning differently, but can even modify the students' actual behavior.

It is not difficult to perceive the misconception of a close link between physical appearance and school performance, as if a different way of walking or communicating, a less common way of gesturing, could in themselves be indicative of an inability to learn. This group includes people with physical disabilities, cerebral palsy, Down syndrome, among others. These people are often discriminated against because of their appearance, as they present a set of different physical characteristics, which makes them more easily identified as *disabled*.

This gives rise to a whole network of meanings that have underestimated them, falling short of their true potential. Taking the child with Down syndrome as an example, it is not difficult to understand the still existing relationship between the myth of their inability to be educated and their physical characteristics. Although there is currently reasonable medical information about the syndrome, a more mythical than objective view still rests upon it, revealing a social structure that imposes and legitimizes hegemonic cultural codes. The possibility of performing facial surgery on people with this syndrome is currently a reality.

Starting in the 1960s, a significant movement of opinion began to form in different countries in favor of the educational integration of students with some type of disability. Its objective was to demand satisfactory educational conditions for all these children within regular schools and to raise awareness among teachers, parents, and civil and educational authorities so that they would adopt a positive attitude throughout this process.

The reasons given were, and continue to be, of a very diverse nature. Perhaps the most general and basic is that which is based on criteria of justice and equality. All students have the right to be offered educational opportunities, under the most normalizing conditions possible, that favor contact and socialization with peers of the same age group, and that allow them in the future to integrate and participate in society in a better way. Along with this argument, others of a more specifically educational nature have been proposed. Integration, carried out under the appropriate conditions and with the necessary resources, is positive for students with some type of disability, contributing to their better development and to a more complete and normal socialization.

Furthermore, integration is also beneficial for the rest of the students, since they learn with a more individualized methodology, have more resources at their disposal, and acquire attitudes of respect and solidarity towards their less gifted peers. Reasons were also formulated that referred to the educational system as a whole.

Integration demands greater professional competence from teachers, more complex educational projects, the ability to adapt the curriculum to the specific needs of students, and also greater foresight regarding educational resources of all kinds.

According to Coll (1995, p. 14):

Sometimes it has been stated that integration is an end in itself, that the main objective is for all students to be together in the same school. In many other instances, integration has been described as a process that only affects students with disabilities, that is, the 2% with the most permanent educational needs. Underlying these positions is the idea that integration is a movement that seeks to incorporate students from special educational centers into regular schools, along with all the technical and material resources that exist there: absence of architectural barriers, communication systems, physiotherapy teams, etc.; special education would simply be transferred to the mainstream school.

Criticisms and misinterpretations have contributed to clarifying the concept of integration throughout these years. The concept of educational integration is not something so rigid, with very precise and defined limits. On the contrary, integration is a dynamic and ever-changing process, whose central objective is to find the best situation for a student to develop as well as possible, and can therefore vary according to the needs of the students, the location, and the existing educational offerings. These different ways of achieving integration should be chosen according to the students' possibilities and the characteristics of the educational center, and can be modified as the children's situation changes.

CONCLUSION

It was possible to conclude that inclusion is a topic that has suggested a series of debates, and this study represents a further step in this discussion, which is far from exhausted. Throughout this work, we sought to reflect on a series of factors that prevent inclusive education from occurring systematically within regular educational institutions, whether due to the ineffectiveness of the systems or the unpreparedness of teachers. Within this problematic context, we sought to analyze the meaning of *difference* within an extremely exclusionary society that carries within it strong dominant characteristics. This is reflected in the way people conceive of differences. There is a widespread, erroneous notion that people, in order to be accepted within society, need to be the same, or present characteristics that do not exceed normal standards.

This can even include aesthetic standards. When educational needs are the focus, the story becomes even more complicated, given the immense resistance that regular schools have in accepting children with special educational needs. At best, these children are accepted; however, they are handed over, when in fact they should be integrated, into educational programs that should address their needs.

This research highlights the importance of establishing guidelines that truly guarantee the inclusion and integration of all individuals with educational needs, not only in regular education but also in society, enabling them to produce, create, participate, express opinions, and ultimately exercise true citizenship. Therefore, it is believed that change must begin with the implementation of new educational policies that aim to demystify difference as invalid and promote the supremacy of difference as natural in any heterogeneous society, which, by its very nature, tends to mask reality.

It is concluded that the inclusion of people with special needs in society in general will only be truly achieved when society acknowledges that there are citizens within its midst who seek alternatives and resources to meet their basic needs, and, moreover, the right to be *citizens* and not just *poor wretches* because they have some type of special need. Often, people with special needs are aware of their capabilities and that their disability may impose limitations on performing certain activities; but they also know that this does not imply that they cannot perform every activity. A person with special needs is consciously capable of choosing a task and performing it consciously and actively if they are stimulated and educated to do so.

What can be achieved, in terms of understanding the topic presented, is that special education should be approached from a pragmatic perspective, where the development of public

policies aimed at the target audience in question proves effective. It is pointless to create actions that appear positive in theory but prove useless to the individuals who need them, or even if teachers are unable to implement the procedures in their pedagogical practice.

The inclusion of children with special needs in regular schools should follow parameters that align with their potential, not merely a desire to force inclusion. The existence of laws addressing inclusion does not guarantee its effectiveness or efficiency, as it lacks appropriate methodologies and strategies for implementation, proper monitoring, and training/capacity building for professionals working with this population.

The idea of educational inclusion is to enable all children to experience broad social interaction, allowing them to break down prejudices regarding the limitations of each participant. Even though it is claimed to be a right, this is much deeper than a mere social right; it is about breaking paradigms regarding people with special needs and their relationship with life and existence.

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